

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CORD LIPID PROFILE IN NORMAL AND LOW BIRTH WEIGHT TERM NEONATES

Author: DR. A.PAVITHRAA, FINAL YEAR POSTGRADUATE, DEPARTMENT OF
PAEDIATRICS, TRICHY SRM MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH
CENTRE, IRUNGALUR, TRICHY.

Corresponding author: DR. BELGIN PREM KUMAR, PROFESSOR, DEPARTMENT OF
PAEDIATRICS, TRICHY SRM MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH
CENTRE, IRUNGALUR, TRICHY.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Birth weight serves as a critical predictor of neonatal health and long-term metabolic outcomes. The Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (DOHaD) hypothesis suggests that adverse intrauterine conditions may program metabolic pathways, predisposing individuals to cardiovascular disease in adulthood. Cord blood lipid profiles provide valuable insights into early metabolic programming and may serve as biomarkers for future cardiovascular risk assessment.

Objective: To measure and compare cord blood lipid parameters between normal birth weight and low birth weight term neonates.

Methods: A cross-sectional comparative study was conducted at the Department of Paediatrics, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Tamil Nadu, from February 2025 to July 2025. Sixty term neonates were enrolled and divided into two groups: low birth weight (<2.5 kg, n=30) and normal birth weight (\geq 2.5 kg, n=30). Umbilical cord blood samples were collected at delivery for lipid profile analysis, including total cholesterol, triglycerides, very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol levels.

Results: Low birth weight neonates demonstrated significantly elevated lipid levels compared to normal birth weight neonates: total cholesterol (80.63 ± 5.47 vs 61.40 ± 8.54 mg/dl, $p < 0.001$), triglycerides (52.87 ± 8.49 vs 36.97 ± 4.06 mg/dl, $p < 0.001$), VLDL cholesterol (20.53 ± 6.11 vs 7.40 ± 3.35 mg/dl, $p < 0.001$), and LDL cholesterol (42.37 ± 19.31 vs 28.50 ± 10.59 mg/dl, $p < 0.001$). HDL cholesterol levels showed no significant difference between groups (26.60 ± 6.61 vs 26.17 ± 7.45 mg/dl, $p = 0.813$). Gender analysis revealed significantly higher HDL cholesterol in female neonates (28.30 ± 7.54 vs 24.04 ± 5.49 mg/dl, $p = 0.017$). A significant association was observed between primigravida status and low birth weight ($p = 0.009$).

Conclusion: Low birth weight term neonates exhibit a distinctly altered cord blood lipid profile characterized by elevated atherogenic lipid fractions. These findings support early metabolic programming concepts and highlight the potential utility of cord blood lipid assessment for identifying neonates at risk for future cardiovascular complications.

Keywords: Cord blood lipid profile, Low birth weight, Metabolic programming

Introduction:

Birth weight is a major indicator of the health of neonates and a predictor of long-term metabolic outcomes in them. A birth weight of less than 2500 grams is defined as Low Birth Weight (LBW), and this is one of the major public health concerns affecting low and middle-income countries. UNICEF (2021) says around 14.6% of all births worldwide are said to be LBW, which results in higher morbidity and mortality⁽¹⁾. Recent scientific data support the claim made by the Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (DOHaD) hypothesis, which states that adverse conditions during foetal life can lead to permanently altering the physiology of the individual, resulting in an increased risk of developing non-communicable diseases in adulthood^(2,3).

Adequate nutrition is a highly crucial component of foetal growth and development, with lipids playing a major role in energy metabolism, cellular structure, and signalling pathways needed for organogenesis and maturation⁽⁴⁾. The umbilical cord lipid profile at birth in neonates is being recognised as a vital marker of early metabolic risk assessment and of future potential to develop cardiovascular complications in adulthood. Deviations in the umbilical cord lipid metrics reflect the intrauterine nutritional status of the neonates and may indicate changes that predispose individuals to atherogenic processes later in life⁽⁵⁾.

Various studies assessing the relationship between birth weight and umbilical cord lipid parameters have yielded conflicting results, resulting in uncertainty in the field. For example, a study done in Uttar Pradesh reported LBW neonates having higher lipid concentrations when compared to normal birth weight (NBW) neonates, while the study done in Nepal showed the reverse findings^(6,7). These inconsistencies mark the vast complexity of neonatal lipid metabolism, which might be determined by various external conditions like maternal, genetic, perinatal factors, gestational age at birth, regional dietary practices and socioeconomic influences.

Although multiple neonatal cohorts have been studied for the relationship between LBW and altered lipid parameters, a direct comparison of the cord lipid metrics between LBW and NBW in the local population is inadequately explored, hence this current study was devised to evaluate and compare the cord blood lipid profiles in normal birth weight and low birth weight babies to understand the metabolic disparities that may arise and to explore potential interventions to mitigate associated risks.

Objectives:

To measure and compare the cord blood lipid parameters of normal birth weight and low birth weight term neonates.

Materials and Methods:

The present study was designed as a cross-sectional comparative study, which was conducted at the Department of Paediatrics, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, from February 2025 to July 2025. A total of 60 neonates born at term were enrolled in the study and distributed into 2 groups of 30 each.

Inclusion Criteria:

Babies born at term (≥ 37 weeks of gestation) weighing ≥ 2.5 kgs were included in group A, while term babies weighing < 2.5 kgs were included in group B.

Exclusion Criteria:

Preterm births (< 37 weeks of gestation), post-term births (> 42 weeks of gestation), neonates born with congenital anomalies or metabolic disorders and neonates born to mothers with gestational diabetes mellitus and hypertension.

Methodology:

The study was carried out after obtaining the proper Institutional Ethics Committee approval and written informed consent was obtained from the parents of the neonates before being included in the study. At birth, the neonates were weighed using an electronic weighing scale and included in the groups accordingly. At the time of delivery, 5 ml of umbilical cord blood was collected, and it was subjected to lipid analysis along with the routine investigations done at birth.

The data was entered into Microsoft Excel 2024 and analysed using IBM SPSS 26.0. Categorical data was expressed as frequencies and percentages, and comparisons between 2 categorical variables were done using the chi-square test, while descriptive measures such as mean, standard deviation values of all the continuous data were calculated as the data was normally distributed. Comparison of mean values of lipid profile between the normal and low birth weight categories was carried out using the Student's T independent test.

Results:

Out of the 60 neonates included in the study, 27 (45%) were males, while 33 were females (55%). Figure 1 depicts the distribution of males and females among the 2 groups. It was observed that the difference in gender distribution among LBW and NBW neonates was not statistically significant ($p = 0.436$). Figure 2 shows the spread of primiparity and multiparity among the 2 study groups, and a statistically significant association was seen between parity and LBW ($p = 0.009$).

The results in Table 1 show that there was a statistically significant difference in mean values of almost all the lipid profile parameters among LBW and NBW neonates, except for the high-density lipoprotein. LBW neonates had a 31.3 % increase in total cholesterol, a 43%

increase in triglycerides, a 177.4% increase in VLDL cholesterol and a 48.7 % increase in LDL cholesterol when compared to NBW neonates, while the HDL cholesterol remained almost the same. Table 2 shows that there was no statistically significant difference in the mean values of the lipid profile parameters among males and females, except for HDL cholesterol, where females had a higher HDL concentration when compared to males. Table 3 shows that there was no statistically significant difference in the mean values of the lipid profile parameters among primiparous and multiparous births, except that VLDL cholesterol concentrations were much higher among primiparous births when compared to multiparous births in the study.

Figure 1: Distribution of gender among the study groups

Figure 2: Distribution of parity among the study groups**Table 1: Association between lipid profile parameters and birth weight of the study participants**

Lipid Profile Parameters (mg/dl)	Birth Weight of Neonates		t-test	p-Value
	Low	Normal		
Total cholesterol	80.63 ± 5.47	61.40 ± 8.54	10.386	<0.001
Triglycerides	52.87±8.49	36.97±4.06	9.254	<0.001
Very Low-Density Lipoprotein	20.53±6.11	7.40±3.35	10.321	<0.001
Low-Density Lipoprotein	42.37±19.31	28.50±10.59	3.449	<0.001
High-Density Lipoprotein	26.60±6.61	26.17±7.45	0.236	0.813

Table 2: Association between lipid profile parameters and gender of the study participants

Lipid Profile Parameters (mg/dl)	Gender		t-test	p-Value
	Male	Female		
Total cholesterol	70.0±12.23	71.85±11.98	0.590	0.558
Triglyceride	42.93±9.58	46.55±10.87	1.353	0.181
Very Low-Density Lipoprotein	13.04±7.43	14.73±8.87	0.789	0.433
Low-Density Lipoprotein	32.33±16.42	37.97±17.20	1.289	0.202
High-Density Lipoprotein	24.04±5.49	28.30±7.54	2.451	0.017

Table 3: Association between lipid profile parameters with parity

Lipid Profile Parameters (mg/dl)	Parity		t-test	p-Value
	Primi	Multi		
Total cholesterol	71.02±12.03	70.45±12.23	0.182	0.857
Triglyceride	44.91±10.38	44.35±10.27	0.210	0.834
Very Low-Density Lipoprotein	35.43±8.23	13.55±8.08	10.36	<0.001
Low-Density Lipoprotein	35.43±16.95	34.16±16.51	0.293	0.771
High-Density Lipoprotein	26.38±6.98	26.55±7.47	0.09	0.928

Discussion:

Our study provides a valuable insight into the cord blood lipid metric changes between LBW and NBW neonates, contributing to the understanding of early metabolic programming and its potential for cardiovascular complications later. The study shows that LBW neonates have significantly higher cord blood lipid metrics when compared to their NBW counterparts; this pattern is broadly consistent with most of the published literature exploring the relationship of umbilical cord blood lipid values with birth weight, which says LBW neonates have a more atherogenic cord blood lipid profile at birth. The study also demonstrated that there was no significant difference in HDL cholesterol between the groups, which is parallel to the findings of the studies done by Nithya et al and Karla AK et al ^(8,9). The similarity in the results substantiates the hypothesis that intrauterine growth restriction will result in compensatory metabolic changes leading to altered lipid profile values at birth. The mechanism driving these changes may include adaptive responses to intrauterine

nutrition not being adequate, and as a result, the foetus strives to achieve energy efficiency (optimal storage and utilisation) through the altered lipid metabolism. HDL cholesterol not being altered at birth between the groups points toward an interesting finding, as HDL cholesterol is often considered a protective factor against cardiovascular disease; this lack of notable difference suggests that even though the pro-atherogenic lipids are heightened at birth in LBW neonates the preventive lipid component might not be affected at birth or its metabolism might be influenced differently.

Contrasting evidences are seen in the published literature, notably Chernenkov et al observed that extremely low birth weight neonates with intrauterine growth retardation had significantly lower total and LDL cholesterol levels when compared to their higher birth weight peers. These findings were also similar to the findings of the study done by Rashmi Y et al, which reported preterm small for gestational age neonates having lower levels of LDL and HDL cholesterol versus their appropriate for gestational age counterparts^(10,11). This difference in the study findings when compared to our study might be because of including only term neonates as study participants.

The study revealed negligible gender-based differences in cord blood lipid parameters, with only HDL cholesterol being significantly increased among female neonates. This may reflect the early gender specific variations in lipid metabolism that could be contributing to the well-established cardiovascular protection of females during their reproductive years. The absence of significant differences in the other lipid parameters among males and females shows that metabolic changes linked to LBW are influenced mostly by the intrauterine nutritional status and development while rather than gender specific prenatal determinants. This discovery might have significant therapeutic ramifications, denoting that birth weight-related metabolic changes affect both sexes equally, with the exception of HDL cholesterol.

Limitations:

The different limitations of the study should be recognized. The cross-sectional study design inherently fails to establish a causal relationship between birth weight and the cord blood lipid levels at birth. The comparatively small sample size may restrict the generalisability of the study findings. Moreover, we had not assessed the maternal lipid profile and dietary habits of the mother, which might provide valuable insight into the reasons for the observed underlying disparities.

Future directions:

Future research into the subject ought to concentrate on carrying out longitudinal studies tracking the neonates into adolescence and adulthood to check if the lipid profile disparities observed at birth are persisting and translate into cardiovascular risk. Examining

the underlying molecular changes, including the genetic expression variations and epigenetic alterations, would give a clear picture of the metabolic programming processes. Intervention studies investigating the effects of maternal nutritional supplements or lifestyle changes on cord blood lipid metrics would bring about clear insights for evidence-based treatments for preventing the adverse changes. The formulation of standardised protocols for cord blood lipid assessment, reference ranges tailored to the corresponding gestational age and birth weight would enhance the clinical utility of the parameter.

Conclusion:

The study shows LBW neonates have significantly higher cord blood lipid parameters when compared to NBW neonates. The significant association of a primiparous mother having an LBW neonate, coupled with the female-specific HDL cholesterol increase, provides additional knowledge into the complex factors influencing the neonatal lipid metabolism. These findings endorse the notion of early metabolic programming and underscore the potential significance of cord blood lipid evaluation as a means to identify newborns predisposed to future cardiovascular complications.

Conflict of interest: None

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